

TEACHING ENGLISH TO A1 LEVEL LEARNERS THROUGH RHYME

Samanova Shaxlo Baxtiyorovna

Scientific Advisor, Teacher in the Department of English
Teaching Methodology №3 in Uzbek State World Languages
University, shahlosamanova134@gmail.com

No'monova Munisaxon Akmalovna

Bachelor student of Uzbekistan State World Languages
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15172007>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 31th March 2025

Accepted: 4th April 2025

Published: 8th April 2025

KEYWORDS

children, learn, rhymes, song,
vocabulary, music, activities

ABSTRACT

This article explores the effectiveness of using rhymes and songs in teaching English to young learners. The importance of teaching English as a foreign language to young learners needs a special approach because young learners have unique characteristics and their own learning styles. Songs, chants, and rhymes are examples of enjoyable activities for children. The main goal of this article is to highlight the importance of using rhymes and songs in teaching English as a foreign language to young learners. Their functions, criteria for election, and ways of presenting them to the class will also be analyzed. Since English has become an international language, more and more people are learning English, and they are learning it at an early age.

Worldwide, English has emerged as the primary language of communication, and early exposure to the language in a classroom setting is growing in popularity. In many Asia nations, including Uzbekistan, where I live, English is taught starting in primary school. Learning English starts at the age of 6 and 7.

Children learn their first language through rhymes and poems as they grow older. Rhymes and songs are not only the most significant spoken language, but they also represent the children's initial exposure to mother tongue communication. When their parents speak and frequently play out finger games and nursery songs, they listen and respond. Their closest caregivers sing them lullabies before they go to sleep, or they attempt to mimic short tunes by chattering. Thus, rhymes and songs help kids feel close to others, establish a unique link with their human surroundings, and have a significant impact on how well they pick up their first language.

Teaching English to young learners requires engaging and interactive approaches that make learning enjoyable and effective. Among the various techniques, rhymes and songs have proven to be powerful tools in early language education. Their rhythmic and repetitive nature helps children absorb new words, improve pronunciation, and develop listening skills.

Rhymes, particularly nursery rhymes, offer numerous benefits that facilitate language acquisition among children. Rhymes, and songs are excellent resources for teaching children a foreign language since they learn best when engaged in engaging activities. In actuality, they are the resources that enable kids to learn in a fun setting without feeling the strain of picking up a foreign language.

Rhymes, and songs are rich in vocabulary, employ real language, and allow kids to benefit from their musicality and repetition, which helps them pick up new vocabulary. Students instinctively pick up and get a lot of language input when they listen to them again. Additionally, they support the development of a calm and pleasant environment in the foreign language classroom, inspiring pupils to learn and bringing joy and excitement. Rhymes, and songs work wonderfully as a part of an ESL program for children, for a non-native speaker at the beginning stage it is clearly easier to sing or recite a rhyme in English than it is to communicate personal information, wants or needs. The rhythm and rhymes naturally appealing to a child, the child is eager to be a part of the rhythm and to participate in reciting the rhyme. A class in which every child feels welcomed as a participating member is a vital factor in effective teaching. Sharing the rhymes and songs as a group relaxes the tensions of competition and of inhibition. Rhymes and songs are easy to memorize, the children derive visible satisfaction and confidence from this newly acquired fluency that comes so quickly.

Using Rhymes and Songs

Any class can start, continue, or conclude with the use of rhymes and songs. In the language classroom, they can be used in a variety of ways, including as brief warm-ups to begin classes, to introduce new language, to practice and revise language, to shift the tone, or to grab everyone's attention. We must choose songs that are appropriate for the age group we are teaching and clearly state which language skills (pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, spelling, etc.) we will be practicing or reinforcing when we use music in our English classes. To fully analyze the possibilities of each song and rhyme, we can construct the following record chart.

Playing the song or rhyme for pupils to listen to.

Singing the song or rhyme by ourselves, using mime, gestures or visual aids to represent high frequency words or expressions (flashcards, pictures, mime, puppets..)

Reading and singing the song with the whole class.

Rhymes and songs and can be recited by ourselves, while showing the

accompanying pictures and then children could recite them along with us. And here is a list of what we can do with a song adapted from Tim Murphey

(1992: 9-10) and other resources of activities in teaching English through songs, and selected some activities which are suitable for children:

1. Listen
2. Sing, whistle, tap, and snap fingers while we listen
3. Sing without listening to any recording
4. Use songs and music to set or change an atmosphere or mood, as 'background furnishing'
5. Use songs and music to make a social environment, form a feeling of community,

dance, make friends.

6. Study grammar
7. Practice selective listening comprehension
8. Translate songs
9. Write dialogues using the words of a song
10. Dictate a song
11. Use a song for gap-fill,
12. Use music for background to other activities
13. Practice pronunciation, intonation, and stress
14. Break the routine
15. Do choral repetition
16. Teach vocabulary
17. Teach culture
18. Have fun

If we look at this list carefully, we can see that all four skills (speaking, reading, listening, and writing) can be very well and equally practiced.

Twinkle, twinkle, little star,

How I wonder what you are!

Up above the world so high,

Like a diamond in the sky.

The Role of Rhymes and Songs in Vocabulary Development

Children acquire language more effectively when learning is fun and interactive. Rhymes and songs introduce new vocabulary in a context that makes words easier to remember. Repetition reinforces language retention, while melodies aid in recall. Many English nursery rhymes, such as *"Twinkle, Twinkle, Little Star"* and *"The Wheels on the Bus,"* provide learners with commonly used words and phrases, helping to expand their linguistic repertoire.

In addition to vocabulary acquisition, rhymes and songs expose children to grammatical patterns naturally. Phrases and sentence structures become internalized as children sing along, allowing them to recognize syntactic patterns without explicit instruction. The predictability of rhyming words also aids in phonemic awareness, which is crucial for reading and spelling skills. A piece of music can amuse and delight while also altering the mood of a classroom. Since children naturally appreciate music, English language instructors all around the world employ engaging and encouraging methods to help kids learn and acquire the language. For young learners, poetry and music are also crucial components of learning a foreign language. Music being a source of motivation, interest and enjoyment, it is much easier for children to imitate and remember language very effective in children language class as children love to repeat and mimic words and sounds. Thus, through this kind of activity they naturally pick up the

In addition to helping learners become familiar with the stress and intonation of words, songs also help them memorize the rhythm with which words are spoken or sung, and they become familiar with parts of the foreign culture, viewing it as an enrichment for their own lives. In effect, it is good to stimulate children's interest in the new language, to bring fun and variety to learning, to provide a relaxed atmosphere, to motivate to learn to be active, to give encouragement, even to children who are shy or slow learning.

REFERENCES:

1. Murphey, T. (1992). Music and Song. Oxford University Press.
2. Pinter, A. (2017). Teaching Young Language Learners. Oxford University Press.
3. <http://learnenglishkids.bri>
4. Sariçoban, ". & Metin, E. (2000). Songs, verse and games for teaching grammar, The Internet TESL Journal. Retrieved 11th January 2011 from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/SaricobanSongs.html>
5. Zanatta, Th. & Herrera, M. (2000) New English Parade, Pearson Education

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY